

Does the electromagnetic field degenerate at absolute zero? An experimental proposal

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Abstract.- *In previous papers the author has suggested the possibility that the observed radiation arrow and the absence of magnetic monopoles are manifestations of a new symmetry of the electromagnetic field in time. This symmetry would consist of two mirror field versions, which degenerate at special time transitions, such as the absolute zero of temperature. One of the effects of this electromagnetic degeneracy at 0 K is presented here as a way to check the validity of this hypothesis.*

Keywords: *Electromagnetic degeneracy, parity violation, absolute zero, magnetic monopole*

1 Introduction

Time irreversibility produces many observable phenomena, for instance, the Universe expansion since the Big Bang (the cosmological arrow), or the irreversible propagation of the electromagnetic field, uni-directionally from sources to sinks, (the radiation arrow). For the latter arrow, however, there is no good theoretical reason that could possibly justify such irreversibility. Indeed, the classical electromagnetic theory has exhaustively searched the symmetry by assuming two different kinds of charged monopoles (electric and magnetic), associated to the observed electromagnetic field [1]. The magnetic monopoles were not observed physically, but introduced artificially for symmetry reasons. However, despite the experimental effort, magnetic monopoles have never been found [1-3].

In previous papers, the author has offered a symmetric solution for the radiation arrow, which, in tune with the cosmological arrow, may explain the absence of magnetic monopoles that were presumably generated in the Big Bang. The solution consists of extending the domain of Time out of its known limits, where a mirror version of the conventional electromagnetic field should be defined [4,5].

Strange as it may seem, this model fits with the existence of cosmological borders of time, such as the Big Bang and the absolute zero of temperature, and with other natural asymmetries, as, for instance, the mentioned absence of magnetic monopoles and the parity violation phenomena in weak and strong interactions. But still there is a need for a definite experimental proof that let unequivocally discern its validity. This paper presents an experimental proposal for this purpose.

2 The electromagnetic degeneracy hypothesis

The electromagnetic degeneracy hypothesis is suggested in [4,5] as a way of symmetrisation of Maxwell's equations in time. This model acknowledges the handedness of the actual electromagnetic field associated to the time forward-direction, and proposes a mirror version for the time-backward one. The role played by the electric and magnetic fields in the new version is inverted with regard to the conventional field, which suggests rather extraordinary physical conditions for the transition between both time-directions. The transitions have been called “time borders”, and identified in Refs. [4,5] with singular points of the cosmological Time: the Big Bang, and the absolute zero, as time —or energy— milestones which would mark the limits of domain for each field version. The name “degeneracy hypothesis” comes from the exchange of handedness between both field versions at both sides of the border¹, meaning the exchange of roles *electric-magnetic*, and the degeneracy of **E** and **B** at the border itself.

If it exists, the new mirror field proposed would be defined beyond the known time limits, which, on the other hand, are essentially unachievable². Still, its effects would be noticeable in the vicinity of the transitions, with expected and foreseeable phenomena that could be detected and measured. This paper precisely aims to study those noticeable consequences of the existence of this new field, and how it could be experimentally proven (or disproven) in a definite and concrete way. But first, let us review the matches of this hypothesis with already observed phenomena: the absence of magnetic monopoles and the parity violation in weak and strong interactions.

2.a Missing magnetic monopoles

This paper's hypothesis offers a straightforward explanation for the inexistence of magnetic monopoles in Nature: the presumably degeneracy of the electric **E** and magnetic **B** fields that occurs at time borders, should occur in the Big Bang too, since, as the “origin” of Time, it is the first and more obvious time border.

This field degeneracy in the Big Bang would make two different kinds of monopole redundant, for the single kind of field —the degenerated one— existing in the border. For reasons of economy of resources and symmetry, there would be only one kind of monopole, whose behaviour as *electric* or *magnetic* would depend on which side of the time border is being observed from. Away from the Big Bang in the time-forward domain, it would seem that there are no magnetic monopoles. Hence, the asymmetry of matter (represented by the asymmetry of monopoles) would be linked to the asymmetry of radiation, with both being only apparent, as a consequence of the partial viewpoint from only one side of the border [4,5].

¹ The handedness is what imprints the role of the electromagnetic vectors, according to the convention: A right-handedness means **E** playing the cause and **B**, the effect, (time forward), while a left-handedness means the opposite. At the border, the electromagnetic fields exchange handedness, and both roles, played by **E** and **B**, degenerate.

² The absolute zero is forbidden by the Third Law of Thermodynamics, and the Big Bang is taken as the very origin of Time, marking the limit of the existence of time itself in modern Cosmology. This paper's hypothesis, however, suggests that these temporal limits are not real, but just apparent, or say, inflexion points of time between the two kinds of electromagnetic propagation.

2.b Parity violation in weak interactions

Parity violation, ever since Wu's famous experiment, has been attributed to the weak interaction. However, something which is usually forgotten is that Wu's experiment had to be performed just above absolute zero (about 0.01 K) [6,7], that is to say, it was performed *very near a time border*, and hence, the electromagnetic degeneracy could also play a role in the parity violation. Indeed, according to this paper's hypothesis, near the absolute zero the fields would degenerate, and the applied \mathbf{B} starts to behave like an electric field, provoking the exit of electrons in its opposite direction, just as an electric field would do (\mathbf{B} 's behaviour, though, would not be perfectly electric, but a degenerate magnetic-electric mixture).

It could be replied that Wu's experiment already ruled out the possibility that the parity violation was an effect of the magnetic field. The proof performed at that time, though, consisted of keeping the magnetic field constant, while the temperature was increased [7]. The parity violation ceased, and that fed the belief that the magnetic field could not be responsible for the parity violation, since it had not been modified.

However, this conclusion could be wrong if the parity violation is a combined effect, *magnetic field & temperature*, as this paper's hypothesis suggests. If that were the case, the effect of the magnetic field degeneracy would only show up precisely near the absolute zero, and that is why the parity violation would be immediately lost as soon as we move away from that zero-temperature point. In my view, in order to rule out the possibility that the parity violation was an effect of the electromagnetic degeneracy, there are two complementary proofs that should be done: 1) to apply an increasing magnetic field, in a constant temperature environment close to the absolute zero, in order to check whether in these conditions the electron acceleration depends on the magnetic field magnitude, and 2) to *decrease* the temperature, while keeping the magnetic field constant. If in both cases the parity violation were stronger, then there would be no doubt about the electromagnetic degeneracy at work³.

2.c Parity violation in strong interactions

While parity violation in the weak interactions is known since Wu's experiment in 1956, the possibility of parity violation in strong interactions has not been known till very recent experiments carried out in the Relativistic Heavy Ion Collider (RHIC) at Brookhaven National Laboratory [8]. The experiment achieved high enough energy levels to break up protons and neutrons into a quark-gluon plasma at the temperature of several trillion degrees Celsius, surprisingly being able to reproduce the same conditions when the Universe was one microsecond old, just after the Big Bang.

In these extreme conditions, the strong magnetic field produced by the plasma also provokes an effect of charge separation, with up quarks, (positive) moving along the magnetic field lines, and down quarks, (negative), against, in the opposite direction. This would constitute, if confirmed, a violation of parity in strong interactions. This

³ The failure of any of these proofs would not mean necessarily that the degeneracy fails, though. In the first one, for instance, the parity violation degree could remain constant if the magnetic component of the degenerate field grows at the same rate as the electric component does.

phenomenon is called the *chiral magnetic effect*, which basically addresses how an imbalance of handedness can produce an electric current [9].

For the author, it was hard to expect that the electromagnetic degeneracy could ever be observed at the Big Bang, because of its unimaginable extreme conditions. However, this experiment at the RHIC is perhaps another hint of its validity: again, the same charge separation along a magnetic field, and again, very near a time border (the Big Bang, in this case). The suspicious coincidences between two parity violation phenomena of such a disparate origin, (the strong and the weak interactions), reinforce the idea to unify them in one explanation: the degeneracy suffered by the magnetic field at time borders. Its validity, however, should be checked experimentally.

The scientific team at Brookhaven has already carried out this experiment at lower energies, in order to verify that the apparent parity violation vanishes [10]. The degeneracy hypothesis could have anticipated the result: The parity violation was lost at *lower* energies, in the same way that in Wu's experiment it was lost at *higher* energies. The reason is that the electromagnetic degeneracy only works in the vicinity of the border, where the trade-off between handedness and fields can occur, —still, there is the need to estimate theoretically the requisite degree of proximity to become apparent.

Both experiments, Wu's (weak) and Brookhaven's (strong interaction), show how at time borders *left* and *right* start to become distinguishable, at the same time that the *electric* and *magnetic* fields start to degenerate (and vice versa: far from the border, \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} are distinguishable, while *left* and *right* degenerate), This indicates an intimate, balanced relationship between space and time, so far unexplained.

3. Experimental Proposal: Thomson's experiment at 0 K

In the previous section, complementary tests on former experiments of parity violation have been suggested, for checking the degeneracy of the *magnetic field* —either near the absolute zero (low energy), or the Big Bang. (high energy)—. However, the degeneracy hypothesis foresees not only the degeneracy of the magnetic, but also of the electric field, hence this hypothesis would not be fully tested till the *electric* degeneracy were not proven in the same extreme conditions.

Indeed, in the same way that the parity violation in weak and strong interactions suggests a possible “electrification”, —or electric mutation— of the magnetic field, the electric field should also show a similar “magnetization”, —or magnetic mutation—, partly behaving as a *quasi*-magnetic field near time borders, which should be observable. In order to verify this, the proposed test is Thomson's famous experiment, now performed near the absolute zero (presumably easier than reproducing the Big Bang conditions). As it is well known, Thomson's experiment gave the charge-mass ratio of electrons, by applying a vertical electric field on a bunch of electrons shot horizontally. The measured deviation of the parabolic trajectory in the vertical axis is related to the mentioned ratio [11].

In normal conditions of temperature, the electric field would behave as *pure-electric*, deviating the electrons just vertically, and their parabolic trajectories would form a more or less symmetrical impact pattern around the vertical y-axis (see figure 2.a). However,

near the absolute zero, if the electric field starts to behave as a *quasi-magnetic* field, it would deviate the pattern slightly to the left (see figure 2.b). This would clearly constitute a parity violation, provoked by electric field degeneracy near a time border. (Obviously, the same deviation, but to the right, would be expected for positive charged particles. For protons, though, it should be stretched and less apparent, due to their higher mass).

Figure 2: Thomson's experiment. Impact pattern on the screen, for electrons shot horizontally from a frontal viewpoint. The applied electric field points upwards. a) In normal conditions of temperature, the impacts are regularly distributed around the vertical y-axis (in shadow). b) Near the absolute zero, the electrons suffer an additional deviation towards the left-hand side, appearing distributed mostly to the South-West.

Apart from the charge-mass ratio and the velocity of the electrons, the lateral pattern deviation Δ would depend on the percentage of the electric field $E_{\%}$ which mutes into magnetic, which presumably would increase with the proximity to 0 K. Based on

classical electromagnetic techniques, Δ can be roughly estimated as $\Delta \sim \frac{d^2}{2} \frac{q E_{\%}}{m v c}$,

where q/m is the charge-mass ratio of the particle, v is its velocity, c is the velocity of light, and d , the horizontal distance from the shot-point to the screen. A precise determination of the pattern deviation Δ would require the use of relativistic-quantum techniques for the estimation of the mentioned percentage $E_{\%}$ at each temperature.

Conclusions

In this paper, an experiment is proposed to check the validity of the hypothesis of electromagnetic degeneracy at time borders. It consists of Thomson's experiment, necessarily performed in the vicinity of the absolute zero. This paper's hypothesis foresees an effect of parity violation, associated to the degeneracy of the electric field near the 0 K. Other complementary experiments for double-checking the possible magnetic degeneracy acting in former experiments of parity violation have also been suggested.

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